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KỶ YẾU

HỘI THẢO KHOA HỌC QUỐC TẾ 2025
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CHUYỂN ĐỔI KINH TẾ XANH
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AND REGIONAL SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT

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17. Raviv, M., & Lieth, H. (2008). *Soilless Culture: Theory and Practice*. Vương Quốc Anh.
18. Reznik, Popov, Podplietnii, & Popova. (2020). Financial support for the development of joint territorial communities. *Test Engineering and Management*.
19. Reznik, N., Dolynskiy, S., & Savchuk, A. (2022). Tasks of sustainable development of Israeli agriculture: its achievements and opportunities of cooperation for Ukraine. *Economics, Finance Management Review*(4), 4-17. doi:<https://doi.org/10.36690/2674-5208-2022-4-4>
20. Seidman, G. (2008). Unexceptional for once: Austerity and food rationing in Israel, 1939-1959. *Southern California Interdisciplinary Law Journal*, 18(95), 95-130.
21. Sne, M. (2005). *Drip Irrigation Manual 2005 - Israel*. State Of Israel.
22. Tal, A. (2007). To make a desert bloom: The Israeli agricultural adventure and the quest for sustainability. *Agricultural History*, 81(2), 228-257. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1215/00021482-81.2.228>
23. Tổng cục Thống kê. (2021). *Kết quả điều tra nông thôn, nông nghiệp giữa kỳ: Nhà xuất bản Thống kê*.
24. Tuyên, P. (2024). Phát triển kinh tế tuần hoàn trong nông nghiệp bền vững tại Việt Nam hiện nay. *Tạp chí Điện tử lý luận Chính trị*.
25. Viên, T. Đ. (2023). Phát triển nông nghiệp Việt Nam: Vấn đề đặt ra và một số giải pháp. *Tạp chí Cộng sản*.
26. Yablochnikov, S., Kuptsov, M., Omelchenko, O., Gupta, S. K., Reznik, N., Hatsko, A., & Sakovska, O. (2019). Modelling of informational counteraction between objects in economy. *International Journal of Engineering Advanced Technology*, 8(6), 3797-3802. doi:<https://doi.org/10.35940/ijeat.F9394.088619>

THE EUROPEAN UNION ENGAGEMENT ON CLIMATE ACTIONS WITH COUNTRIES FROM ASIA-PACIFIC REGION CASE STUDY: ESTABLISHING THE JUST ENERGY TRANSITION PARTNERSHIP WITH VIET NAM

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Abstract: *In order to achieve the climate goals of the Paris Agreement and manage the transition to sustainable, climate-resilient and climate-neutral development, rapid and deep greenhouse gas reductions were necessary. Consequently, at the 26th UN Climate Change Conference in Glasgow (COP26) it was announced the first "Just Energy Transition Partnership" (JETP) as a new plurilateral structure for accelerating the phase-out of fossil fuels. Taking into account that the fight against climate change has reached a critical turning point in 2025 - a year marked by geopolitical tensions and economic risks - the main purpose of this study is to highlight the instruments and tools used by EU to deepen climate cooperation with other countries, especially within existing JETPs with countries from Asia-Pacific region. In this context, considering the Viet Nam's commitments announced at the 26th UN Climate Change Conference in Glasgow (COP26), including a net-zero emissions target by 2050, a subsequent aim of this study is to deepen and clarify the aspects related to the adoption and implementation of the Just Energy Transition Partnership (JETP) with Viet Nam.*

Keywords: *UN Climate Change Conference; EU engagement on climate action; Just Energy Transition Partnership with Viet Nam; Resource Mobilization Plan.*

1. Introduction

At the UN Climate Change Conference (COP21), held in Paris in December 2015, the participating countries adopted an international agreement to address climate change that requires deeper emissions reduction commitments from all countries - developed and developing. Therefore, the Paris Agreement charted a new course in the effort to combat global climate change, requiring countries to make commitments and progressively strengthen them, its overarching goal being to hold "the increase in the global average temperature to well below 2°C above pre-industrial levels" and pursue efforts "to limit the temperature increase to 1.5°C above pre-industrial levels"⁽¹⁾.

1. Article 2.1(a) of the Paris Agreement on climate change
- https://unfccc.int/sites/default/files/resource/parisagreement_publication.pdf

It is important to note that the EU and all its member states have signed and ratified the Paris Agreement and are strongly committed to its implementation. Thus, by ratifying the agreement, the EU and its countries are legally bound by its goal of keeping global temperatures within safe limits. In this context, the EU and its Member States, building on the strong track record of domestic climate action, engaged, together with many other partners, in a broad "High Ambition Coalition" across different regional groupings of developed and developing countries. EU engagement on climate action was emphasized by the Council in its conclusions on European climate diplomacy after COP21, identifying "climate change advocacy as a strategic priority in diplomatic dialogues, public diplomacy and external policy instruments"⁽¹⁾.

As a result, it can be said that climate action is currently an integral part of the EU's foreign policy agenda. Through diplomacy and cooperation initiatives, the EU aims to advance global climate action and support partner countries in their efforts to tackle climate change.

2. Instruments and tools used by EU to deepen climate cooperation with countries from Asia-Pacific region

To deepen climate cooperation with countries from Asia-Pacific region, the EU uses a range of instruments and tools, including: High-Level Dialogues on climate-related issues, Green Alliances and Green Partnerships, as well as Just Energy Transition Partnerships (JETPs).

In this regard can be mentioned the High-Level Dialogue on Climate Change between the European Union and Japan, in which senior officials agreed to deepen their bilateral cooperation, work together towards achieving climate neutrality and tackling climate-related challenges. In 2021, both sides moved to a new phase in their cooperation on climate change, green transition and other environmental issues following the launch of the EU-Japan Green Alliance. In this partnership, both the EU and Japan share the aim of becoming climate-neutral by 2050, the cooperation within the Green Alliance being focused on five areas: pursuing a cost-effective, safe and sustainable energy transition by adopting low-carbon technologies, including renewable energy, renewable hydrogen, energy storage, and carbon capture, utilisation and storage; strengthening environmental protection by promoting more sustainable, circular practices in production and consumption, and contributing to the global goal of protecting at least 30% of both land and sea in order to conserve biodiversity; increased regulatory cooperation and business exchange to drive global uptake of low-carbon technologies and environmental solutions that will accelerate the global transition to climate-neutral economies; consolidating existing collaboration on research and development in the areas of decarbonisation projects, renewable energy, and the bioeconomy; and maintaining both parties' leadership on international sustainable finance to help converge on a definition of sustainable investments and ensure consistency and transparency about sustainability-related disclosures⁽²⁾.

1. European climate diplomacy after COP21 - Council conclusions (15 February 2016)

- <https://data.consilium.europa.eu/doc/document/ST-6061-2016-INIT/en/pdf>

2. https://climate.ec.europa.eu/news-your-voice/news/eu-and-japan-commit-new-green-alliance-work-towards-climate-neutrality-2021-05-27_en

Other climate diplomacy engagement in the region includes efforts to establish the EU-Korea Green Partnership in 2023. Taking into account that the EU and the Republic of Korea share the ambition of a climate-neutral future, the Green Partnership is focused on several priority areas: strengthening efforts on combating climate change, including cooperation on climate adaptation, carbon pricing, methane emissions and climate finance; increasing cooperation on environmental issues with a focus on halting and reversing biodiversity loss, forest degradation and deforestation, promoting circular economy and addressing the full life cycle of plastics, as well as the implementation of the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework; supporting a clean and fair energy transition by intensifying cooperation on renewable energies, energy efficiency, renewable and low-carbon hydrogen, a just transition away from unabated coal-fired power generation, batteries and green mobility and Carbon Capture, Utilization and Storage (CCUS); working with third countries to facilitate their green transition, notably in the area of climate change mitigation, adaptation and resilience, the clean and fair energy transition, and circular economy; joining forces in other areas such as business cooperation, sustainable finance, research & innovation, sustainable food systems, sustainability and resilience of supply chains as well as employment and the social dimension of the green transition. In line with the priority areas of their Green Partnership, the EU and the Republic of Korea have also agreed to promote climate action on the international stage, in multilateral and plurilateral fora, notably as major donors of climate finance and as facilitators of a just transition in third countries. The two parties will cooperate to support developing countries and emerging economies with their implementation of climate and environment policies.⁽¹⁾

As a key proponent of international climate action, the EU is committed to sustain cooperation and build partnerships and alliances towards achieving internationally agreed climate objectives. In this regard, the EU promotes the energy transition from coal and other fossil fuels by actively engaging in the so-called "Just Energy Transition Partnerships (JETPs)".

The JETP paradigm was established at the 26th UN Climate Change Conference (COP26) in Glasgow, in the context in which the just transition advanced as a critical factor for enabling a successful shift to a net-zero and resilient economy, almost six years after it was included as a single line within the Paris Agreement. As can be easily observed, the terms "just" and "partnership" are central. The use of "just" underlines that the energy transition must be implemented in an equitable and inclusive manner with regard to its social consequences. In affected populations and sectors, retraining and alternative business models not based on fossil fuels are to be created for this purpose. The use of "partnership" emphasizes that these agreements are tailored to the needs of the recipient country and that local decision-makers are actively involved⁽²⁾.

Therefore, since COP26 in Glasgow, Just Energy Transition Partnerships (JETPs) have emerged as a new collaboration instrument between countries. The JETP with South Africa marked the first step in 2021, and more JETPs have been initiated since then, including Indonesia (2022), Viet Nam (2022) and Senegal (2023).

1. *European Union – Republic of Korea Green Partnership*, https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/ip_23_2816

2. *Just Energy Transition Partnerships* - <https://dgap.org/en/research/glossary/climate-foreign-policy/just-energy-transition-partnerships>

3. The Just Energy Transition Partnership (JETP) with Viet Nam

• *Establishing the JETP with Viet Nam*

On 14 December 2022, the International Partners Group (IPG)⁽¹⁾ and Viet Nam announced the signing of a JETP. It should be remembered that, on the same day, the "EU-ASEAN Commemorative Summit" took place in Brussels, celebrating 45 years of EU-ASEAN diplomatic relations.

As stated in the Political Declaration on establishing the Just Energy Transition Partnership with Viet Nam, the IPG agreed to "mobilise an initial amount of at least \$15.5bn over the next three to five years through a combination of appropriate financial instruments, which should not divert critical development assistance away from existing development funding to support the needs of Viet Nam's just energy transition in accordance with the national framework of public debt and external debt management. Working closely with the Viet Nam Government, IPG members will mobilise \$7.75bn of public sector finance which should be on more attractive terms than Viet Nam could secure in the capital markets. Working closely with the Vietnamese Government and the IPG, the GFANZ Working Group members will work to mobilise and facilitate at least \$7.75bn in private finance, subject to mobilisation of the catalytic public sector finance by the IPG members"⁽²⁾. At the same time, it is shown that "the mobilization of this finance will be enabled by the adoption of the Viet Nam JETP Resource Mobilisation Plan (JETP - RMP) and subject to and in line with all relevant budgetary procedures and consensus on the use of funds and terms on which finance may be provided and a pipeline of opportunities consistent with the Government of Viet Nam's ambition". The JETP - RMP was to benefit from administrative and technical support provided by a Secretariat established to help facilitate support for Viet Nam's just energy transition efforts from the IPG and key stakeholders, including multilateral and bilateral development financial institutions, private sector and others.

The Secretariat for Implementation of the JETP Declaration was established by Decision No. 845/QĐ-TTg on 14 July 2023. According to this Decision, the Secretariat includes Mr. Dang Quoc Khanh (Minister of the Natural Resources and Environment Ministry) – Head of the Secretariat, the Deputy Heads and other members. This will be an organization to assist the Prime Minister - Head of the COP26 Steering Committee in coordinating work related to the JETP Declaration, and at the same time cooperating with international partner groups during the implementation process. Specifically, the Secretariat will advise the Prime Minister to develop and implement the Plan to mobilize resources for JETP implementation, to synthesize information, reports, proposals and recommendations related to JETP implementation, supervise and deal with other related issues. The standing agency of the Secretariat will be the Ministry of Natural Resources and Environment, along with four working groups to support the development and implementation of JETP, including: *General Group*: established by the Minister of Natural Resources and Environment;

1. The IPG is made up of: EU, UK, USA, Japan, Germany, France, Italy, Canada, Denmark, and Norway.

2. *Political Declaration on establishing the Just Energy Transition Partnership with Viet Nam* - https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/statement_22_7724

Institutions, Policy and Investment Group: established by the Minister of Planning and Investment; *Technology and Energy Group*: established by the Minister of the Industry and Trade; *Finance group*: established by the Minister of Finance.⁽¹⁾

• *The Launch of the JETP - RMP with Viet Nam*

Based on Politburo's Resolution 55-NQ/TW on the Orientation of the Viet Nam's National Energy Development Strategy to 2030 and outlook to 2045, Global Coal to Clean Power Transition Statement supported by Viet Nam, the Vietnamese Prime Minister issued Decision No. 1009/QĐ-TTg on the approval of the "Scheme to implement the Political Declaration establishing a Just Energy Transition Partnership (JETP Scheme)" on 31 August 2023⁽²⁾. The JETP Scheme includes all the main contents of the Political Declaration, as well as some initial priorities (offshore wind power, power transmission, energy storage) and also is providing the structure for implementation of JETP, and it is allocating responsibilities for implementation to Vietnamese entities (the JETP Secretariat and Working Groups to Support JETP Implementation).⁽³⁾

The JETP - RMP with Viet Nam was launched by Vietnamese Prime Minister Phạm Minh Chính during the World Leaders Summit at COP28 on 1st December 2023 in Dubai, United Arab Emirates. On this occasion, the International Partners Group (IPG), comprised of the European Union (EU), the United Kingdom (UK), Canada, Denmark, France, Germany, Italy, Japan, Norway and the United States of America, and co-led by the EU and the UK, welcomes and endorses Viet Nam's JETP – RMP.

Regarding the content of the JETP - RMP with Viet Nam, it is as follows:

- Chapter 1 provides this introduction, referring to the JETP Declaration and Viet Nam's policy documents such as Nationally Determined Contribution (NDC), National Climate Change Strategy (NCCS) for the period up to 2050, and a number of energy policies, as well as the Scheme on JETP implementation;

- Chapter 2 gives a brief overview of the international climate policy context, towards net zero emissions by 2050, Viet Nam's commitments to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and respond to climate change and some details on the implementation of JETP in Viet Nam;

- Chapter 3 Overview of investment needs for just energy transition in Viet Nam based on updated NDC and energy policy and the JETP Scheme. It also provides principles and orientations for selecting priority projects for JETP implementation;

1. Decision No. 845/QĐ-TTg on launching the Secretariat for the Political Declaration on establishing the Just Energy Transition Partnership - <https://english.luatvietnam.vn/co-cau-to-chuc/decision-845-qd-ttg-2023-launch-the-secretariat-for-the-political-declaration-on-establishing-jetp-259367-d1.html>

2. Decision No. 1009/QĐ-TTg approving the Scheme for the Implementation of the Political Declaration on Establishing the Just Energy Transition Partnership - https://vepg.vn/wp-content/uploads/2023/09/1009_QD-TTg_31082023_ENG.pdf

3. *Resource Mobilisation Plan Implementing the Political Declaration on Establishing the Just Energy Transition Partnership (JETP)* - https://climate.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2023-12/RMP_Viet%20Nam_Eng_%28Final%20to%20publication%29.pdf

- Chapter 4 discusses finance mobilization, ways of accessing public and private international financial sources, the links to domestic commercial finance, and assessment of feasibility in the current investment context in Viet Nam;

- Chapter 5 provides opportunities for achieving a just energy transition, as there are opportunities for jobs and investment in the renewable energy, energy efficiency and electric transportation value chains. It also discusses issues that need to be addressed in order to achieve social and economic justice for social groups; issues of inequality, poverty, access to energy sources for households and businesses;

- In Chapter 6 the investment priorities to be agreed between national stakeholders, the IPG and GFANZ members⁽¹⁾ are discussed, with different types of support corresponding to the list of potential programs and projects summarized in the Annex I and Annex II and the policy actions in Annex III;

- Chapter 7 provides an overview of policy actions to overcome investment challenges and increase investment in the energy transition, and enable a just energy transition, especially private investment in green, energy-related measures;

- Chapter 8 provides agreements on JETP implementation and governance, including assessment of progress and monitoring activities, communication and international cooperation.

There are strong interlinkages between the issues raised in these 8 chapters. Delivering a just energy transition will depend on the combination of the policy actions, development of projects, and mobilising public and private finance. While different chapters show that there are major challenges in the energy transition, they also demonstrate that there are major opportunities, for reducing greenhouse gas emissions and at the same time ensuring national energy security, increasing both business and employment opportunities, protecting the local environment and improving social equality.⁽²⁾

4. The action plan to implement Vietnam's commitment to use clean energy instead of coal-fired power made at the COP 26

On 12 February 2025, Vietnamese Prime Minister Phạm Minh Chính has approved the plan to implement the Global Coal-to-Clean Power Transition Statement which aligns with Vietnam's commitment to low-carbon development and achieving net-zero emissions by 2050. Thus, according to Decision 266/QĐ-TTg⁽³⁾, the plan aims to mobilize domestic

1. Glasgow Financial Alliance for Net Zero (GFANZ) is a group of private institutions set up at COP26 in Glasgow to provide private sector funding for the global green energy transition. With regard to Vietnam's JETP agreement, a working group of GFANZ members was put together including the Bank of America, Citi, Deutsche Bank, HSBC, Macquarie, Mizuho Financial Group, MUFG, Prudential Plc, Shinhan Financial Group, SMBC Group, and Standard Chartered.

2. *Resource Mobilisation Plan Implementing the Political Declaration on Establishing the Just Energy Transition Partnership (JETP)* https://climate.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2023-12/RMP_Viet%20Nam_Eng_%28Final%20to%20publication%29.pdf

3. <https://datafiles.chinhphu.vn/cpp/files/vbpq/2025/02/266-ttg.signed.pdf>

and international resources for power sector development, adopt co-firing technology with clean fuels, phase out outdated and inefficient facilities, and accelerate renewable energy expansion. By 2030, Vietnam will pilot carbon capture systems at selected aging coal power plants and evaluate the decommissioning of approximately 540 MW of coal-fired capacity at the Pha Lai and Ninh Binh plants if efficiency and emission reduction targets are not met. Additionally, research on biomass and ammonia co-firing will be conducted to lower CO2 emissions, with renewable energy projected to account for 29.2% to 37.7% of the country's energy mix. The Ninh Thuan nuclear power project is expected to be completed within five years. By 2045, Vietnam will develop at least 1,160 MW of clean energy to replace coal power and gradually transition more than 25,000 MW of coal capacity to biomass and ammonia. By 2050, all coal-fired plants will either switch to clean fuels or integrate carbon capture technology, ultimately eliminating coal use in power generation.

5. Conclusions

This year marks 10 years since the adoption of the Paris Agreement at the UN Climate Change Conference (COP21) and, as a result, it is a good opportunity to reflect on the progress made and also the obstacles faced in the ongoing battle against climate change.

In order to reach the goal of the Paris Agreement, the EU has aimed to be climate-neutral by 2050 - an economy with net-zero greenhouse gas emissions, this objective being at the heart of the European Green Deal, and also a legally binding target thanks to the European Climate Law. However, even robust EU environmental legislation is not sufficient to address transboundary and global environmental degradation, nor to sufficiently reduce the impact of the EU's economic activity on natural resources worldwide. The environmental ambition of the European Green Deal will not be achieved by Europe acting alone. That is why international cooperation is essential to confront global environmental challenges and EU's partnerships with countries overseas further strengthen the commitment to jointly tackle global environmental challenges that threaten the future of our planet.

As one of the EU's principal partners in Southeast Asia, Viet Nam has the highest number of agreements with the EU, among these can be mentioned a partnership and cooperation agreement, a free trade agreement, and a forest law enforcement, governance, and trade voluntary partnership agreement.

Within this strong partnership, despite the geopolitical tensions and economic risks that mark the year 2025, the EU is committed to supporting Vietnam's journey towards sustainable and inclusive development, aligning its efforts with the 2021-2030 Vietnam Socio-Economic Development Strategy, the Vietnam Green Growth Strategy, and the EU's Global Gateway and Indo-Pacific Strategies. The EU's engagement is rooted in Vietnam's commitment to the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development and aims to promote a sustainable green transition, highlighted by the Scheme to implement the Political Declaration establishing a Just Energy Transition Partnership.

References

1. Paris Agreement on climate change (12 December 2015), https://unfccc.int/sites/default/files/resource/parisagreement_publication.pdf;
2. European climate diplomacy after COP21 - Council conclusions (15 February 2016), <https://data.consilium.europa.eu/doc/document/ST-6061-2016-INIT/en/pdf>;
3. European Union – Republic of Korea Green Partnership, https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/ip_23_2816;
4. EU - Japan Green Alliance, https://climate.ec.europa.eu/news-your-voice/news/eu-and-japan-commit-new-green-alliance-work-towards-climate-neutrality-2021-05-27_en;
5. Just Energy Transition Partnerships, <https://dgap.org/en/research/glossary/climate-foreign-policy/just-energy-transition-partnerships>;
6. Political Declaration on establishing the Just Energy Transition Partnership with Viet Nam, https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/statement_22_7724;
7. Decision No. 845/QĐ-TTg on launching the Secretariat for the Political Declaration on establishing the Just Energy Transition Partnership, <https://english.luatvietnam.vn/co-cau-to-chuc/decision-845-qd-ttg-2023-launch-the-secretariat-for-the-political-declaration-on-establishing-jetp-259367-d1.html>;
8. Decision No. 1009/QĐ-TTg approving the Scheme for the Implementation of the Political Declaration on Establishing the Just Energy Transition Partnership, https://vepg.vn/wp-content/uploads/2023/09/1009_QD-TTg_31082023_ENG.pdf;
9. Resource Mobilisation Plan Implementing the Political Declaration on Establishing the Just Energy Transition Partnership (JETP), https://climate.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2023-12/RMP_Viet%20Nam_Eng_%28Final%20to%20publication%29.pdf
10. Vietnam Government Porta- <https://datafiles.chinhphu.vn/cpp/files/vbpq/2025/02/266-ttg.signed.pdf>.

TRADE FACILITATION AND FEMALE VALUE ADDED IN GLOBAL VALUE CHAINS: EVIDENCE FROM ASEAN ECONOMIES

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Abstract: *As regional integration deepens in ASEAN, trade facilitation has become increasingly important for promoting inclusive development. This study investigates the relationship between trade facilitation and female value-added in global value chains by constructing a regional scorecard based on trade facilitation indicators and applying a structural gravity model estimated using the Poisson Pseudo Maximum Likelihood method. The analysis draws on bilateral trade data between six ASEAN economies and their major Asian trading partners. Results show that improvements in trade efficiency, institutional capacity, and digital modernization are positively associated with greater female contributions to value-added trade. These findings highlight the critical role of institutional reforms and infrastructure development in expanding economic opportunities for women, particularly those in small and medium-sized enterprises or labor-intensive export sectors. The study also reveals that structural trade barriers and asymmetries in trade partnerships can limit women's ability to move into higher value-added activities. The results suggest that trade facilitation, when combined with gender-responsive implementation, has the potential to foster more equitable participation in regional and global value chains. This research offers timely insights for ASEAN policymakers seeking to align trade reform with broader social inclusion goals..*

Keywords: *Trade facilitation; Global value chains; Female value added; ASEAN; Gravity model; Gender-inclusive trade; PPML estimator*

1. Introduction

Globalization has deepened economic ties worldwide, with ASEAN emerging as a dynamic hub of trade and production. As the world's second most GVC-integrated region after Europe, over 40% of Asia's gross exports are linked to value chains (ADB, 2023). While trade has fueled growth, its benefits remain uneven - especially for women, who despite contributing 66% of global labor, earn only 10% of global income (Kalliny & Zaki, 2024; World Bank, 2022). GVCs, especially in emerging economies like those in ASEAN, are reshaping production and trade. While GVCs can offer women opportunities for income and employment, they often confine them to low-paid, undervalued positions.